

Heart Sutra 波若波羅蜜多心經

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Chinese Buddhism, Buddhist Sutra, Buddhist Traditions, Sino-Tibetan, Korean Religions, Japanese Buddhism, Text, Classical Indo-European, Xuanzang Text, Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Mahayana Buddhism, Indo-Iranian, Sanskrit version, Chinese Buddhist text, Language, Modern Buddhism, Mahayana-Vajrayana Hybrid, Japanese Buddhist Traditions, Sinitic, Canonical texts, Sanskrit, Indo-Aryan, Indo-European, Korean Buddhist Traditions, Mongolian Buddhism, Tibetan Buddhist Traditions, Classical-Middle-Modern Sinitic, Vietnamese Buddhist Traditions

The Heart Sutra represents one of the most prominent texts in the Mahayana Buddhist tradition, being one of the dominant ways in which many people today understand and engage with Buddhism across East Asia. Despite its widespread use across the centuries, the text's origins and provenance are somewhat ambiguous and remain the subject of intense academic debate. Although identified as one of 'Perfection of Wisdom' Prajñāpāramitā sutras, and certainly concerned with the nature of reality as many of these sutra are, marked differences from other sutras, lack of evidence for it prior to the 7th C CE and linguistic factors have raised the prospect that rather than being a product of the early South Asian Sanskrit tradition, something its traditional narrative purports, the text may have originated in China in the medieval period and was subsequently translated into Sanskrit and other languages. Regardless of its origin, there are two related versions of the text in use today, a short, 'canonical' version familiar to most people in East Asia purported to have been translated by the monk Xuanzang 玄奘 (602-664) in 649 and a 'long' version which contains the content of the short version alongside introductory and concluding sections, something commonly seen in other Buddhist sutras. The longer version is often encountered in tantric practices in some Vajrayana communities in Tibet and Mongolia. The shared material of both versions depict the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara, identified in East Asia as Guanyin 觀音, gaining clarity upon meditation that all things are 'empty' and that this fundamental reality is universal to all aspects of human experience, the skandhas. Avalokiteśvara's awakening to this truth sees him address the Buddhist disciple Śāriputra to explain that since everything is empty concepts such as the 'Four Noble Truths' are in themselves empty as well, and it is this understanding, the Perfection of Wisdom, the enlightened beings have realised. The passage ends with a mantra, common in Buddhist sutras, reinforcing the lessons of the text. The text's brevity, simple language and repetitive rhetoric not only allow for ease of memorisation, but also strongly suggest the text is meant for a lay audience. That it encapsulates many of the basic principles of Mahayana Buddhism – the Perfection of Wisdom, value of bodhisattvas, basic Buddhist concepts, etc. – only serves to reinforce its value as a lay teaching tool to familiarise people with Mahayana Buddhism.

Date Range: 649 CE - 2024 CE

Region: East Asia

Region tags: Asia, East Asia

East Asia

Status of Readership:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: The earliest extant version of the text currently known is a copy careved on stone stele in the Yunju temple 雲居寺 in Fangshan 房山 southwest of Beijing. It is dated to 661 CE. Though the text is purported to predate this.

Notes: The Heart Sutra is widely available in a large variety of print forms from pamphlets distributed by Buddhist monasteries, academic translations, to even works of art. There is no specific print source that is regarded as canonical or more deserving of attention in the religious or lay traditions that have used this text.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: https://21dzk.l.u-tokyo.ac.jp/SAT/index_en.html

– Source 1 Description: The SAT Daizōkyō Text Database is a digitised version of the Chinese Buddhist Canon.

– Source 2 URL: <https://library.bdrc.io/>

– Source 2 Description: The Buddhist Digital Archives is an online collaborative platform that collects and stores a wealth of Buddhist texts and literature regardless of sectarian affiliation.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Notes: Earliest transmission is purported to be via translation from oral accounts.

– Incised or Inscribed

Method of inscription

– Chisel

Notes: Earliest extant version of this text is a stone stele dated to 661 in the Yunju Temple 雲居寺 located in Fangshan 房山 in Beijing.

– Printed with moveable type

Number of sheets

– Single sheets

Notes: As printing became common from the 10th C onwards, this text would be frequently printed.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Area of Circulation for the Taijitu Shuo and Tongshu (East Asia)

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Bamboo

Notes: Earliest extant texts would have been written on bamboo which was the common writing medium during the first millennium in China.

– Stone

Notes: As mentioned stone stele containing the text also date from its earliest mentions.

– Paper

Specify type of paper

– Specify: Unknown

Notes: Once printing became commonplace, varieties of different paper would have been the preferred medium to transmit the text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Area of Circulation for the Taijitu Shuo and Tongshu (East Asia)

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Buddhist sutras often existed as orally transmitted texts before being written down. It is thus unknown if the text went through any modifications for writing. Further the ambiguity of the origin of the text, whether it was a Sanskrit text translated into Classical Chinese, or a text that was written in Classical Chinese to begin with, complicates the issue of how 'modified' it would have been.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: There is no evidence of modifications in the earliest attestations of the text.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: The text as a teaching tool has always been widely disseminated, and there is no specific location that a specific 'canonical' version is stored.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: State patronage would be subject to the particular rulers of the various polities at different times. There is no ruler in East Asia that is known to particularly support the Heart Sutra over other Buddhist texts. There have been rulers who have helped and supported Buddhist communities and thus may have helped to promote versions of this text alongside others the communities supported.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Yes

Notes: It is common Buddhist practice to recite texts as a method of meditation. The Heart Sutra's content, brevity and simple language have always made it one of the most common sutras to recite, particularly by lay practitioners.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– Yes

Notes: All sutras are meant to be the word of a Buddha, and the Heart Sutra is meant to be transmitted from Avalokiteśvara. Further, the narrative of how the Heart Sutra arrived in China, being a translation from Sanskrit by the monk Xuanzang 玄奘 (602-664), who would gain fame from the popularity of the fictitious text Journey to the West 西遊記 published in the Ming (1368-1644), has also afforded the text a particular cache amongst lay Buddhist as it has become associated with the great quests of East Asian monks to South Asia to acquire the word of the Buddhas.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– No

Notes: All Buddhist communities are meant to engage in interpretation of the sutras, and Mahayana practices place great strength in lay participation in this endeavour. As such, there is no formal institution that is the sole arbiter of interpretation.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– No

Notes: Buddhist monks are expected to transmit sutras as an act of meditation, however lay members can also participate in this, and the Heart Sutra has often been transmitted in a variety of capacities outside of formal Buddhist institutions.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: There is no single canon that Buddhist texts belong. However, there are a number of dynamic canons that Buddhist communities often turn to, although in theory all sutras are considered valid regardless of sectarian affiliation. The Heart Sutra can be found in both the Chinese Buddhist Canon and the Tibetan Buddhist Canon, beyond being frequently encountered in lay situations.

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– Yes

Notes: The Heart Sutra has been commented upon since its first attestation, and numerous commentaries from notable historical figures, such as the Japanese monk Kūkai 空海 (774-835), are common. These commentaries can be found in the Buddhist canon alongside the original text.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The ambiguity of the Heart Sutra's origins makes determining the earliest language used for it difficult. If it was of South Asian origin, then Sanskrit is purported to be the language of its origin. However, as the sutra is more common in the modern day in East Asia, it is often found in highly vernacularised Classical Chinese.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear how many people would be considered 'Buddhist' as many Buddhist communities do not require confessionalism in their members. This also means that Buddhist sutras, particularly widespread ones such as the Heart Sutra also find themselves used by a number of non-Buddhist communities. The text was, and still is, often used in a lay capacity to teach people fundamental aspects of Buddhism and in the contemporary era has expanded outside of East Asia for this purpose.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Confessionalism is not seen as necessary amongst many people who identify as Buddhists. Whereas proselytisation is less emphasised in Buddhist monastic communities when compared to other religious communities, the Heart Sutra is often used by people wishing to explore Buddhism to understand basic concepts of particularly Mahayana Buddhism.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

Notes: Meditation on sutras is standard practice amongst Buddhist communities both at the elite and lay level. The Heart Sutra is and has always been a popular text to engage in this practice.

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– No

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

Notes: The Heart Sutra has always been a popular text to read and gain an understanding of Buddhism.

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– No

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– No

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: Meditation

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text, as any Buddhist sutra, can be used in large group meditative practices or recitation to large audiences. This is more common in Tibetan and Mongolian communities than in Mahayana traditions.

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As a prominent lay text, the Heart Sutra is often recited or meditated upon by individuals or small groups. This is highly prominent today in Mahayana communities.

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Notes: Buddhist practitioners usually place emphasis on the message of the text over the physical object. Calligraphic traditions abound in East Asia, however, and calligraphic renderings of the text may be appreciated by lay practitioners for their physicality. However, this would be for aesthetic and not religious reasons.

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: Illustrations are found in some versions of the Heart Sutra. However, these are not 'original' to the text and often reflect either reading aids for those with poorer literacy or aesthetic choices from the publisher for sale.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: The debate over the origin of the Heart Sutra makes dating difficult. However, the earliest extant short version so far discovered is dated to 661. It is unclear when the long version was developed, but would have been present by the 14th century when the Tibetan Buddhist Canon was finally compiled.

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Notes: The Heart Sutra is known in both a short form, which is the earliest attested version in 260 characters, and a long version which includes the text of the short version and includes an introductory section and a concluding section. The former is more common across East Asia, while the latter is found in the Tibetan Buddhist Canon.

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– Yes

Notes: The text is used as a mechanism of meditation in many Buddhist and lay traditions.

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The Heart Sutra is included in both the Chinese and Tibetan Buddhist canons. It is also often collected with a number of other sutras in the Prajñāpāramitā tradition.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Authority of the Buddhist Canon is established through convention and discussion amongst Buddhist communities. At certain times, state patronage has also contributed to canonisation efforts, though this is a dynamic and changing process.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?
– Yes

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?
– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?
– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?
– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Notes: The Heart Sutra introduces key concepts that are important to the Mahayana Buddhist tradition, notably the Perfection of Wisdom Prajñāpāramitā ■■■■■■■■■■■■■■■■■■■■■■ 般若波羅蜜多 which refers to the perfected way of seeing reality and the skandha ■■■■■■■■ 蘊 which refer to the ways in which people attach themselves to things. Important Buddhist figures such as Avalokiteśvara ■■■■■■■■■■■■■■■■ 觀音 and Śāriputra ■■■■■■■■■■■■■■■■ 舍利子 are also introduced.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?
– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?
– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?
– No

Beliefs

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– No

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: The Heart Sutra does not assert any hierarchy amongst the supernatural beings it mentions.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Heart Sutra is an exposition of the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara obtaining clarity on the Perfection of Wisdom. Whilst the text does not in itself depict the bodhisattva performing any supernatural feats, this achievement of enlightenment can be understood in this way.

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– No

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: The Heart sutra does mention that other buddhas and bodhisattvas have also attained the understanding of the Perfection of Wisdom, but does not describe them in detail.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– No

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– No

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– No

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– No

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Notes: The Heart Sutra explains that the bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara realises that all methods of understanding existence or 'empty' and thus existence is itself 'empty'. This is hence defined as the Perfection of Wisdom and serves as one of the core understandings of Mahayana Buddhism. Whereas the understanding of reality as empty is not a 'virtue' in a Judeo-Christian convention, the Heart Sutra does purport it to be a necessary, and indeed the supreme, method to achieve enlightenment.

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Notes: The ambiguity of the text's production makes it somewhat unclear as to where it originated. If it emerged from South Asia, it would have been produced in a complex multi-state environment. Should it have originated in East Asia, the society it would have been a part of would have been one of the numerous East Asian empires.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The Heart Sutra is attested to have entered into lay practice very early on, as such there would

not have been one specific element of society that would have controlled the reproduction of the text.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: There are no specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text. At certain times in East Asian history, Chinese emperors have proscribed Buddhist communities or practices, but no direct mention of targeting the Heart Sutra has ever been noted.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: Monastic orders would teach Buddhist sutras to acolytes and at times lay practitioners. The Heart Sutra would have been one of these texts, though there are no special pedagogical methods or educative practices particularly associated with the Heart Sutra over other texts.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No